

Implementation of the Village Development Index in Increasing Development to Anticipate Non-Military Threats in West Kalimantan Province

Muhtar Rifai¹, Zainal Abidin Sahabuddin², Tien Norma Habsari³

¹(Defense Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

²(Lecturer in Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

³(Defense Economics Department, Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: *The Village Development Index puts an emphasis on strengthening regional autonomy. The community assumes that life in the village has a lot of poverty and low strata of life, so that the disparity rate is still too high. Empowerment of village communities is a policy that can answer various problems in development. Village empowerment refers to data found as information about potential resources, cultural values, and village characteristics. Through a descriptive qualitative study, this journal describes the implementation of a building village index based on indicators of social, economic and environmental resilience in enhancing development with the ultimate goal of optimal community welfare in order to anticipate forms of non-military threats. The national ranking of the Village Development Index (IDM) of West Kalimantan Province by Regency in 2019 shows Mempawah Regency has the highest IDM in the Province with an average of 0.7615 with advanced status. Meanwhile, Melawi Regency has the lowest IDM on a provincial scale with an average of 0.5422 being underdeveloped. Based on the IDM status, out of 12 districts, there are 1 advanced district, 6 developing districts, and 5 underdeveloped districts. It means that there are 8.3% of areas where there are potential social, economic and environmental resources, as well as management capabilities for improving the quality of life, welfare and poverty reduction; 50% of the regions have social, economic, and environmental resource potentials, but their management has not been able to optimize; 41.7% of areas have potential social, economic and environmental resources, but they are not yet managed or lacking in management.*

KEYWORDS: *Village Development Index (IDM), Development, Welfare, Non-military*

I. INTRODUCTION

Based on Law of Indonesia No. 6 in 2014 concerning Villages, a village is a legal community unit that has territorial boundaries that are authorized to regulate and administer government affairs, the interests of the local community based on community initiatives, rights of origin and / or traditional rights that are recognized and respected in the government system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The village in the government administration structure is the smallest unit that has an important role and expected to be the starting point for the development of centers of community economic growth. (Ministry of Village, Development of Disadvantaged Areas, and Transmigration - PDPT, 2015).

RI Proclaimer Moh. Hatta said that Indonesia will not shine because of the big torch in Jakarta, but only because of the candles in the village. In President Joko Widodo's Nawa Cita, an important point is

mentioned, namely "Building a Village from the periphery by strengthening regions and villages within the framework of a unitary state". The existence of the Law on Villages gives authority to villages in managing village funds, village assets, and potential resources to increase development and community welfare.

The Village Development Index, abbreviated as IDM, is a government program formed as support in the Government's plan for handling alleviating villages that are still lagging behind towards an independent village, providing data and basic information for the village development process. The village development process itself is based on a combination of three development indicators in the form of social resilience, economic resilience and environmental resilience.

The Village Development Index focuses on efforts to strengthen autonomy. This is done in response to the assumption that life in the village has a lot of poverty and low level of life. To reduce the high rate of disparity, policies are needed that can answer various problems in village development and empowerment.

Village empowerment refers to data found as information about potential resources, cultural values, and village characteristics. Through this empowerment, the related parties hope that the welfare of the community can be achieved optimally in order to anticipate forms of non-military threats.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Implementation

Cleaves argues (A. Aziz Sanapiah and Satyadi Nugroho, 2019) that implementation is interpreted as a process that moves towards targeted policies through administrative and political steps. The final result, in the form of success or failure in implementation, will be evaluated how far the ability to continue and be operationalized like the previous programs. Riant Nugroho (2004) argues that policy implementation factors are carried out in the sequence of policy implementation management. The policy implementation is managed in the following tasks:

1. Strategy implementation is the initial idea before implementing a policy, whether later the policy will be implemented directly or through a derivative policy.
2. Organizing is the formulation of implementation steps, conceptual control, division of work tasks and functions according to human resource capacity.
3. Mobilization and leadership is the application of allocation of resources according to the implementation procedures used.
4. Control is the process of periodic monitoring and evaluation of the concepts that have been implemented.

2.2. The Village Development Index

The Village Development Index, abbreviated as IDM, is an index formed from an aggregate or a combination of 3 indexes which include: Social Resilience Index, Economic Resilience Index, and Village Ecological Resilience Index. IDM has a legal basis, namely Law no. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages and Minister of Village Regulation, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration (Permendes PDRT) No. 2 of 2016 concerning the Village Development Index. The IDM aims to provide references and information for development, especially for villages, as well as the basis for determining the level of progress and independence of a village.

The formula for calculating the Village Development Index:

$$IDM = 1/3 (IKS + IKE + IKL)$$

Noted :

IDM: Village Development Index

IKS: Social Resilience Index

IKE: Economic Resilience Index

IKL: Environmental Resilience Index

Each dimension is built based on a series of variables derived into the indicator set. Each indicator has a score range of 0 to 5. The explanation is that if the score is higher, then something is getting more positive.

$$Y = \frac{\text{Total Score X}}{\text{Maksimum Value of X}}$$

The initial "Y" is a component in the index consisting of an index of environmental resilience, an index of economic resilience, and an index of social resilience, while the initial "X" is an indicator of each index.

Table 1
Indicators of the Village Development Index (IDM) in West Kalimantan Province

Social Resilience Index (IKS)	Economic Resilience Index (IKE)	Environmental Resilience Index (IKL)
1. Access to Health Facilities	1. Production Diversity	1. Environmental quality
2. Docter	2. Shops	2. Disaster prone
3. Midwife	3. Market	3. Disaster response
4. Other Health Workers	4. Grocery store/shop	
5. BPJS Membership Level	5. Post and Logistics	
6. Access Poskesdes	6. Bank and BPR	
7. Integrated service post activities	7. Credit	
8. Access to Elementary School/Madrasah Ibtidaiyah	8. Economic Institute	
9. Access to Junior High School/Madrasah Tsanawiyah	9. Lodging	
10. Access to High School/Vocational High School	10. Public Transportation Mode	
11. Availability of Early childhood education programs	11. Regional Openness	
12. Availability of PKBM	12. Road Quality	
13. Course Availability		
14. Library Availability		
15. The Mutual Cooperation Tradition		
16. The Intensity of Mutual Cooperation		
17. Availability of Public Access/Means		
18. Sports Community		
19. Sports Activities		
20. Religious Diversity		
21. Language Diversity		
22. Communication Diversity		
23. environmental security post		
24. Environmental safety system		
25. Conflict		
26. People with Social Welfare Problems		

27. Ordinary Wide School (SLB)		
28. Electric Access		
29. Phone Signal		
30. Internet		
31. Citizen Internet Access		
32. Toilet/Closet Access		
33. Trash		
34. Drinking Water		
35. Bathing And Washing Water		

Source : Village Community Empowerment Service (PMD) in West Kalimantan Province 2021

The data above explains that there are several indicators for The Village Development Index which are divided into each index, the Social Resilience Index has 35 indicators, the Economic Resilience Index has 12 indicators, and the Environmental Resilience Index has 3 indicators.

Table 2
The Village Development Index

Independent	Advanced	Developing	Disadvantaged	Very Disadvantaged
A advanced village that has the ability to carry out village development to improve the quality of life and life as much as possible for the welfare of the village community with social resilience, economic resilience, and ecological resilience in a sustainable manner.	Villages that have the potential for social, economic and ecological resources, as well as the ability to manage them to improve the welfare of the Village community, the quality of human life, and alleviate poverty.	The village has the potential to become a advanced Village, which has the potential for social, economic and ecological resources but has not managed them optimally to improve the welfare of the Village community, the quality of human life and alleviate poverty.	The village which has a resource potential of social, economic, and ecological but not yet, or less manage them in an effort to increase the welfare of the village community, the quality of human life and experience poverty in its various forms.	Villages that are susceptible because of the problem of natural disasters, economic shocks and social conflict that is incapable of managing the resource potential of social, economic, and ecological, as well as the experience of poverty in its various forms.

Source : Permendes PDDT No. 2 of 2016

The table above explains that Village progress and independence are described into 5 (five) levels, including: Independent (green), Advanced (blue), Developing (yellow), Disadvantaged (light blue), and Very Disadvantaged (red). The conversion of IDM status values is as follows: a) Independent Village: > 0.8155; b) Advanced Village: 0.7072 <IDM ≤ 0.8155; c) Developing Village: 0.5989 <IDM ≤ 0.7072; d) Disadvantaged Villages: 0.4907 <IDM ≤ 0.5989; e) Very Disadvantaged Village: IDM ≤ 0.4907.

2.3. Development

Development according to Siagian (2009) is a series of conscious and planned efforts for the growth and change of the nation, state and government towards modernity with the aim of nation building. Meanwhile, according to Suharyanto, development is part of the process of change towards a better condition. Development can also be interpreted as a coordinated effort to create more alternatives for every citizen legally in order to fulfill and achieve his most human aspirations. (Nugroho and Rochmin Dahuri, 2004).

2.4. Non-military threat

Non-military threats in the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 3 of 2002 concerning Defense are called non-military threats which are a form of threat that uses non-military factors which are deemed to endanger the sovereignty, territorial integrity and safety of the entire nation and state. Non-military threats can come from abroad or can come from within the country. Non-military threats are classified into several dimensions such as ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, technology, public safety, and legislation at the local, regional and national levels. (www.kemhan.go.id)

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted using a qualitative approach. A qualitative approach is a research that is intended to provide an understanding of the phenomena experienced by research subjects. For example, motivation, perception, behavior, action, and others are holistically described in the form of words and language, in a particularly natural context which is utilized through various natural methods. (Lexy J. Moleong, 2008).

The research method used in this research is descriptive method. The descriptive method according to Travers has the aim of providing an overview of the nature of something that is ongoing in the research process and examining the causes of a particular symptom. (Husein Umar, 2014). The data collection technique that researchers used is a combination of several data collection techniques, namely:

- a. Interview with Ir. Yuslinda, MM. as the Head of the Community and Village Empowerment Service of West Kalimantan Province.
- b. Documentation research which is an analysis of collections of data and information through books, journals, laws, official records and online government data.

The data that has been obtained, tabulated, is continued through analysis that leads to the implementation process of The Village Development Index in increasing development in order to face non-military threats in West Kalimantan Province.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on table below shows the value of the The Village Development Index of West Kalimantan Province by Regency in 2019. The national ranking shows Mempawah Regency has the highest IDM level in the Province with an average of 0.7615 with an advanced status. Meanwhile, Melawi Regency has the lowest IDM on a provincial scale with an average of 0.5422 being underdeveloped. Based on the IDM status, out of 12 districts, there is 1 advanced district, 6 developing districts, and 5 underdeveloped districts. This means that there is 8.3% of areas where there are potential social, economic and environmental resources, as well as management capabilities for improving the quality of life, welfare and poverty reduction; 50% of the regions have social, economic, and environmental resource potentials, but their management has not been able to optimize; 41.7% of the area has potential social, economic and environmental resources, but has not managed yet.

Table3
Indeks Desa Membangun Kalimantan Barat Per Kabupaten 2019

No	National Ranking	Regency	IKS	IKE	IKL	IDM Score	Number of Villages	IDM Level
1	11	Mempawah	0,8784	0,7172	0,6869	0,7615	60	Advanced
2	80	Kubu Raya	0,7598	0,5543	0,7111	0,6751	117	Developing
3	84	Kayong Utara	0,7851	0,5826	0,6527	0,6763	43	Developing
4	173	Sambas	0,7491	0,5388	0,6484	0,6454	193	Developing
5	226	Kapuas Hulu	0,7382	0,5282	0,6113	0,6259	278	Developing
6	244	Sanggau	0,7315	0,4959	0,6270	0,6181	163	Developing
7	281	Bengkayang	0,7169	0,4801	0,6159	0,6043	122	Developing
8	294	Sekadau	0,7318	0,4866	0,5770	0,5985	87	Disadvantaged
9	310	Ketapang	0,7044	0,4985	0,5731	0,5920	253	Disadvantaged
10	371	Sintang	0,6563	0,4094	0,6038	0,5565	390	Disadvantaged
11	379	Landak	0,6721	0,4340	0,5380	0,5480	156	Disadvantaged
12	381	Melawi	0,6642	0,3975	0,5649	0,5422	169	Disadvantaged

Source : Data Kemendes PDDT (secondary data)

Based on each index, there is a Social Resilience Index of 8.3% of the regions that are independent, namely in Mempawah Regency, which means that they have been able to build their villages according to their social potentials to create sustainable community welfare; 58.3% of the regions have developed, namely in the districts of Kubu Raya, Kayong Utara, Sambas, Kapuas Hulu, Sanggau, Bengkayang, and Sekadau, which means they have been able to build villages with the social potential that they have to create prosperity; 33.3% of the regions have developed, namely in the districts of Ketapang, Sintang, Landak, and Melawi, which means they have social potential in development, but their implementation is not yet optimal. For this reason, the government needs to take a social approach through a top-down movement to identify indicators that need to be addressed for further policy making, especially on health, education and accessibility.

There is an Economic Resilience Index of 8.3% of areas that have advanced, namely in Mempawah Regency, which means that they have been able to develop villages through their economic potential to create welfare; 50% of areas are still underdeveloped, namely in the districts of Kubu Raya, North Kayong, Sambas, Kapuas Hulu, Sanggau, and Ketapang, which means they have economic potential, but havenot well managed so that increased welfare is disrupted due to persistent poverty; 41.7% of areas are very underdeveloped, namely in Bengkayang, Sekadau, Sintang, Landak, Melawi districts, which means that this area is vulnerable to economic shocks and the ability to overcome economic problems does not exist, so there is still a lot of poverty.

There are still many areas in West Kalimantan that are economically underdeveloped and very underdeveloped, but it does not mean they do not have the resources. In West Kalimantan Province BPS data, it is stated that regional potentials such as Agriculture, Industry, Trade, and Construction are the contributors to Provincial GRDP above 10% per year. This explains that the government must step in to optimize what it already has, so that slowly poverty can be suppressed and prosperity is created.

There is an Environmental Resilience Index 8.3% of areas have advanced, namely in the District of Kubu Raya, which means that they have been able to develop villages through their environmental potential to create welfare; 58.3% of areas have developed, namely in Mempawah, North Kayong, Sambas, Kapuas Hulu, Sanggau, Bengkayang, and Sintang districts, which means that they have environmental potential in development, but their implementation is not yet optimal; 33.3% of areas are still underdeveloped, namely in the

districts of Sekadau, Ketapang, Landak, Melawi, which have environmental potential, but have not / are lacking in their management.

Table 4
Average Of The Village Development Index Of in West Kalimantan Province

Village Level	2018	2019	2020
Independent	1	87	214
Advanced	53	182	332
Developing	372	767	907
Disadvantaged	928	781	566
Very Disadvantaged	677	208	12
Total	2031	2031	2031

Source : Village Community Empowerment Service (PMD) in West Kalimantan Province 2021

In a period of two years, West Kalimantan succeeded in increasing the number of Independent Villages in 2018, which only had one village, increasing to 214 Independent Villages in 2020. In 2020, there are 12 villages of Very Disadvantaged Villages in Ketapang Regency; 4 villages, Sintang; 1 village, and Landak; 7 villages. The rapid development of the village has made the IDM score of West Kalimantan Province to 15th rank with 0.698 and above the national average of 0.646.

The potential of local resources available in West Kalimantan Province can be utilized in accelerating regional development such as increasing economic growth, alleviating poverty, creating jobs for the community. Management readiness is a strategic step to strengthen the national defense system to deal with non-military threats that can disrupt national stability, such as border violations, separatism, piracy, terrorism, radicalism, theft of natural resources, and drug abuse.

Facing non-military threats can be answered by creating social welfare. This is in accordance with the intent of the 2018 - 2023 West Kalimantan Provincial RPJMD which reads, "Improving the welfare of the people of West Kalimantan by reducing poverty and unemployment, reinforcing the government's support for disadvantaged communities and areas, eliminating discrimination in various aspects of social services, and accelerating the downstream process by strengthening the synergy between the agricultural sector in a broad sense and the mining sector and the manufacturing sector."

The acceleration of community welfare is supported by accelerating the increase in the status of the Village Development Index. Several approaches that can be implemented are the area / cluster approach which includes: 1) village-based IDM around oil palm plantations, 2) village-based IDM around mining companies, 3) village-based IDM at state borders, 4) village-based IDM on the coast.

The strategy for implementing approach activities is to collaborate / collaborate involving various parties, namely elements of the Provincial Government, District Government, Village Government, Army / Police, Vertical Agencies, Universities, the community and also involves private companies in West Kalimantan Province.

The large number of private companies in West Kalimantan are required to have a role in empowering communities and villages. Companies can help, both in terms of infrastructure and non-infrastructure. For example, infrastructure empowerment is the development of Integrated service post activities, Early childhood education programs, environmental security post, Village Library, Sports Facilities. Meanwhile, examples of non-infrastructure are fire suppression equipment, rubber boats / canoes, evacuation boards, economic improvement training for rural communities, health services.

The government is running its strategy by activating the existing potentials such as BUMDes with an injection of funds. This is the position of the Provincial Government as a facilitator for the Central Government to directly develop villages. Apart from the Central Government as a vertical agency, several horizontal agencies that also build are universities, elements of the TNI-POLRI and elements of the Provincial Government such as Office of Cooperatives for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Department of Public Works and Public Housing, Agriculture Service, Banking. These agencies offer cooperation in the form of programs, such

as capital loans, subsidies, stimulus, skills upgrading. As for the benefits received to strengthen the Village Development Index in the context of realizing community welfare.

V. CONCLUSION

5.1. Conclusion

Based on the research discussion above, there are several conclusions that can be drawn regarding the implementation of the Village Development Index in increasing development in order to anticipate non-military threats in West Kalimantan Province, including:

1. Community welfare is created through the acceleration of regional development based on the Village Development Index with several approaches including:
 - a. Village-based IDM around oil palm plantations;
 - b. Village-based IDM around mining companies;
 - c. IDM based on villages at the border of the country,
 - d. IDM based on villages on the coast.
2. To carry out the strategy to increase the Village Development Index, the related parties that must cooperate and collaborate are Provincial Government, District Government, Village Government, Army-Police, Vertical Agencies, Universities, Communities, and private companies.
3. Contributions made to increase the Village Development Index are as follows:
 - a. Private companies empower rural communities by building infrastructure and non-infrastructure.
 - b. The Central Government optimizes BUMDes through funding.
 - c. Higher education conducts community service.
 - d. TNI-POLRI collaboration and cooperation.
 - e. Provincial government elements such as Office of Cooperatives for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Department of Public Works and Public Housing, and Agriculture Office carry out government programs according to their duties.
 - f. Banking provides convenience in capital.

5.2. Suggestion

1. The government should pay more attention to the Economic Resilience Index, which is still underdeveloped and very underdeveloped level.
2. Related parties must continue to work together and collaborate so that IDM will be better in the future with an average level of "advanced", this is important in terms of anticipating non-military threats, especially since West Kalimantan Province is in the land and sea border areas with other countries.

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